

UNIVERSITY OF
BATH

Assessing the Key Economic and Political Determinants of Chinese FDI into the EU

Edward West

Economics BSc

25 April 2025

Abstract

This dissertation investigates the key determinants of Chinese Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) into European Union (EU) countries, contributing to a judgement on the relative importance of economic and political variables. The study employs time-fixed effects regression models and leverages Fathom Consulting's (2024) China Capital Flows Tracker dataset to distinguish between the determinants of total, greenfield, and M&A investment flows. This paper finds that GDP is a key driver of Chinese investment across the EU and a strong trade relationship is also seen to positively affect the number of FDI deals. This suggests that economic motivations are central in determining Chinese investment flows into the EU. A conclusion that is reinforced by the result that being part of the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) is associated with fewer Chinese FDI deals for EU members. However, it is also found that institutions, a more political variable, positively affects Chinese M&A FDI into EU countries.

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank my dissertation supervisor, Imran Shah, for sharing his expertise and guidance with me throughout this project. I would also like to extend my gratitude to my family and friends for their support and advice.

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1. Introduction

China's prominence in the global economy has transformed in recent decades and this is exemplified by the drastic change in their Foreign Direct Investment (FDI). China's Outward Foreign Direct Investment (OFDI) has increased from \$30 billion in 2005 to a peak of \$418 billion in 2016 (Fathom Consulting, 2024). Consequently, there has been significant growth in the influence and importance of Chinese multi-national corporations (MNCs). The growing influence of China has been noticed in the European Union (EU) with discussions around 'de-risking' from China beginning in recent years (Brinza et al., 2024). President of the European Commission, Ursula von der Leyen has defined de-risking as "minimising risks arising from certain economic flows (...), while preserving maximum levels of economic openness and dynamism" (Andersson and Lindberg, 2024, p.8). A lot of the discourse on de-risking focusses on trade dependencies, however there is also concern from the EU around the substantial rise in FDI from China (Köncke and De Graaff, 2024). The magnitude of these investments are significant with Capital Flows into the EU from China accumulating to \$460 billion since 2005 (Fathom Consulting, 2024).

Receiving FDI can have many benefits and is found to contribute to economic growth and technological advancements (Kurtishi-Kastrati, 2013). However, Chinese investment increases economic ties through Chinese ownership of capital and companies in the EU. Considering the concerns about potential over-reliance, the extent to which China's investment in the EU has grown could be alarming to EU policymakers.

Investigating the key determinants of Chinese FDI may indicate what motivates Chinese MNCs when investing in the EU. This is crucial in answering how concerned EU members should be about the volume of investment. There have been concerns about the possibility of strategic intentions behind Chinese OFDI (Thi Tuong Anh et al., 2022). Understanding the drivers behind Chinese investment in the EU could help suggest whether there are political or strategic motivations. For example, Buckley et al. (2007) find that countries with poor institutions attract Chinese FDI indicating that there could be political motivations. Similar findings for investment into the EU could suggest that Chinese FDI should be received with some caution. However, if economic determinants are the main drivers behind investments, the increase could be due to more Chinese

MNCs identifying opportunities to invest in the EU. In this case, while investment will increase economic ties and not achieve any ‘de-risking’, there may be a more limited threat of geopolitical influence.

This dissertation aims to identify the key determinants influencing Chinese FDI flows into EU countries on an aggregate level, with FDI also split into greenfield investments and mergers and acquisitions (M&A). The relative importance of determinants that represent economic and political motivations may imply the extent to which the EU should be concerned about inward Chinese FDI. A detailed deal-level analysis of potentially politically motivated investments does not take place. Therefore, the possibility of strategic investments cannot be disregarded in this dissertation, only found to not be as prevalent as investments that have economic determinants.

There is extensive existing literature studying the determinants behind FDI and also specifically behind Chinese FDI, but these can vary depending on the region that China is investing in (Mumtaz and Smith, 2018). This dissertation adds to the less extensive research focussing on the drivers of Chinese FDI into European countries, specifically into the EU. In addition, the detailed dataset used in this study provides greater accuracy in measuring Chinese OFDI flows, avoiding unreliable conclusions from biased data often seen in existing literature (Sutherland and Anderson, 2015). Furthermore, by including both key economic and political variables, conclusions on the relative importance between them can be made from the research in this dissertation.

The paper is organised as follows. Section 2 provides a background to Chinese FDI into the EU, covering the trends and composition of this investment and explaining some relevant concepts for this dissertation. Relevant academic literature is discussed in section 3, beginning with findings on general FDI determinants and then looking closer at previous research on the drivers behind Chinese FDI. This study’s contribution to the existing literature is also presented in this section. In section 4, the panel data used in this research is discussed, including a description of the Capital Flows dataset and the potential key determinants chosen as explanatory variables. Section 5 presents the econometric approach undertaken. The results of the regressions estimated are presented in section 6 alongside a discussion of these findings. Section 7 concludes, discussing the key findings and policy implications of this research as well as addressing the limitations.

2. Background

This section provides contextual information behind the rise of Chinese OFDI globally and into the EU, which is due largely to China's strategy in becoming a global economic power. The scale and composition of Chinese FDI across the EU is also displayed, highlighting the types of investment and the countries and sectors that attract the most inflows.

2.1 China's global strategy

China's striking economic growth in recent decades has been echoed by the rise of Chinese MNCs. China have become a central part of the global economy following their 'go out' global strategy adopted at the start of the century (Sauvant and Chen, 2014). This strategy was seen in China's accession to the WTO in 2001 but also in the government's encouragement of Chinese enterprises to become international (Sauvant and Chen, 2014). The government support received helped Chinese MNCs to be internationally competitive (Larçon, 2009), which is seen in the large volumes of overseas investment from Chinese enterprises.

The apparent desire of China to become a global power has not faded, as was seen in 2013 with the introduction of the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI). The initiative is open to all countries and looks to promote infrastructure connectivity with China as a core hub (Yu, 2024). Many countries, including some EU members (Nedopil, 2025), have become part of the BRI. Since its introduction, Chinese companies have expanded foreign investment and developed new economic ties with countries along the BRI (Yu, 2024). Chinese OFDI isn't restricted to just BRI countries, but the initiative does convey the strength of China's global position. The success of Chinese enterprises globally has been reflected in the increase of Chinese investment in Europe too.

2.2 Chinese FDI into the EU

This study focusses on China's FDI into the EU which was more than 4 times higher in 2023 than in 2005, despite the United Kingdom (UK), a major recipient of Chinese investment, no longer being an EU member. The growth from 2005 to the peak value of investments in 2017 is even more astounding, as seen in Figure 1. Although the value of investment flows from China began at a low base, it has increased to a significant amount

for the EU (Hui and Tse, 2025).

Figure 1: Value of Chinese FDI into the EU

Source: Fathom Consulting (2024)

The Global Financial Crisis and European Debt Crisis created opportunities for Chinese investors to acquire European enterprises (Ma and Overbeek, 2015). This is one factor that led to Chinese FDI in the EU exceeding EU investment in China for the first time in 2010 (Shuyan and Fabuš, 2019). The importance of M&A investment in the development of FDI relations between China and the EU is clearly demonstrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2 - Value of Chinese M&A and Greenfield FDI into the EU

Source: Fathom Consulting (2024)

Although the value of Chinese FDI into the EU has mainly been driven by M&A investment, both types of investment are important to consider. Furthermore, Figure 2 also displays that in the most recent years, greenfield investment has become a larger

proportion of Chinese investment in the EU.

The value and volume of Chinese greenfield FDI deals into the EU has significantly grown since 2005, as illustrated in Figure 3. The increasing number of greenfield investment deals conveys the rising market activity of Chinese companies throughout the EU. This upward trend is seen prior to the introduction of the BRI in 2013 and reached a peak in 2018. The volume of deals has subsided in recent years but remains at a significantly higher level than the early 2000s. Additionally, the value of greenfield deals hit a peak in 2022 and is also at a significantly higher level than the early 2000s.

Figure 3 - Value and number of Chinese Greenfield FDI deals in the EU
Source: Fathom Consulting (2024)

Many studies ignore the unique nature of different investment types (Dreger, Schüler-Zhou and Schüller, 2017) but this study considers both total FDI and its breakdown into greenfield investment and M&A to offer greater analytical detail. The distribution of Chinese total, greenfield and M&A FDI across the EU is presented in Table 1. The table displays the EU members who have received the most investment from Chinese companies since 2005. It is evident that the most developed countries were the largest recipients for both types of investment, perhaps with the exception of Hungary who have received large volumes of greenfield investment.

Table 1: Top EU Host Countries for Chinese FDI, 2005 - 2023

	Total	Greenfield	M&A
1	UK*	UK*	UK*
2	Germany	Germany	Germany
3	France	Hungary	France
4	Italy	Spain	Italy
5	Netherlands	France	Netherlands
6	Spain	Italy	Spain
7	Finland	Finland	Finland
8	Hungary	Poland	Sweden
9	Sweden	Sweden	Portugal
10	Portugal	Netherlands	Ireland

Source: Fathom Consulting (2024)

**Includes investment in the entire period to the UK despite the country leaving the EU in 2020.*

Furthermore, the importance of the sectors that have received investment may provide some justification for the concerns of EU policymakers. Table 2 presents the sectors where Chinese enterprises have invested most in the EU during the period studied in this dissertation. Looking at total FDI, ‘Computers & Electronics’ and ‘Coal/Oil/Gas/Renewables’ are the most invested in sectors (Fathom Consulting, 2024). Hrynkiw and Lavrijssen (2024) argue that FDI affecting the energy sector in the EU should be subject to high scrutiny by EU members. This is supported by the findings of Otero-Iglesias and Weissenegger (2020), who conclude that the acquisition of a 35% stake in CDP Reti by a state-owned Chinese enterprise allows China geopolitical influence over Italy’s electricity grid.

Table 2: Top EU Sectors for Chinese FDI, 2005 - 2023

	Total	Greenfield	M&A
1	Computers & Electronics	Computers & Electronics	Coal/Oil/Gas/Renewables
2	Coal/Oil/Gas/Renewables	Real Estate/Property	Computers & Electronics
3	Real Estate/Property	Telecommunications	Real Estate/Property
4	Auto/Truck	Coal/Oil/Gas/Renewables	Auto/Truck
5	Financial Services	Transportation/Warehousing	Financial Services
6	Mining	Auto/Truck	Mining
7	Transportation/Warehousing	Metals	Consumer Products/Retail
8	Consumer Products/Retail	Leisure/Entertainment/Hotels	Industrial Machinery
9	Industrial Machinery	Chemicals/Plastics	Food/Beverages
10	Leisure/Entertainment/Hotels	Consumer Products/Retail	Transportation/Warehousing

Source: Fathom Consulting (2024)

Examining the composition of Chinese investment in the EU provides valuable context. It conveys the importance of understanding the determinants of Chinese investment in the EU for policymakers since China’s global strategy has led to significant investment in some important sectors, such as the energy sector. Considering the EU is currently “prioritising the reduction of vulnerabilities and the enhancement of resilience” with respect to EU-China relations (European Commission, 2024), there is reason to be wary of these investments. However, the extent to which the EU’s China policy should focus on Chinese FDI into the EU ought to be guided by what the key determinants of Chinese investment are. This could indicate whether motivations are generally guided by economic decisions or political strategy.

3. Literature Review

The drivers behind FDI have been investigated at great length for decades. The eclectic paradigm, explaining that overseas investment results from a firm’s ownership, location and internalisation advantages (Dunning, 2000), has been a central theoretical framework in FDI studies. In analysing what determinants drive FDI into certain countries, researchers investigate the location advantages of this framework but are yet to reach a consensus on what the most important determinants are.

The range of regions focussed on in studies could be one reason for the lack of clear consensus. Potential determinants may have varying effects on FDI across regions. This

is evidenced by Asiedu (2002) who finds different factors attract foreign investment into sub-Saharan African countries compared to the rest of the world. Piteli (2010) also finds that FDI determinants vary depending on the development of the host country, emphasising the heterogeneity in FDI determinants across the globe. Therefore, some findings of key determinants in the existing literature may not be applicable to the case of Chinese investment in the EU.

To present an overview of the existing literature related to this topic, the key determinants often found in general literature as well as studies focussed on Chinese FDI are discussed. Finally, this dissertation's contribution to the established literature is outlined.

3.1 Findings on key determinants of FDI in existing literature

Aggregate variables have often been explored as possible determinants of FDI. Scaperlanda and Mauer (1969) investigate the effect of market size, economic growth and tariff discrimination on FDI. They evidence that market size is an important determinant. However, this early study is limited as there is a lack of data and the authors only focus on US investment in Europe. Khachoo and Khan (2012) come to the same conclusion for market size in their more recent study based on a sample of 32 developing countries. Looking solely at their study, it could be argued that this finding may be restricted to developing countries but the importance of market size as a determinant is a conclusion replicated in many studies across a long period of time. Chakrabarti (2001) reports that this finding is robust regardless of the region analysed. Although market size is commonly found to have a positive effect on FDI, researchers have come to conflicting conclusions for other determinants.

Trade is found to be an important determinant in some studies, especially when considering the impact of trade openness for developing countries in attracting FDI (Demirhan and Masca, 2008; Rogmans and Ebbbers, 2013). Kumari and Sharma (2017) consider 20 developing countries across Asia and find market size and trade openness have a positive influence on receiving FDI using fixed effects (FE) and random effects (RE) models. However, the trade variable's result is not statistically significant at the 5% level, resulting in some uncertainty regarding the robustness of this result. The importance of trade remains somewhat uncertain across the current literature with other studies finding that it is not a relevant determinant (Blonigen and Piger, 2014).

Furthermore, the estimated impact could depend on how trade is measured and the variable that is used, as is discussed later.

Another economic variable with an ambiguous impact on FDI is research and development (R&D). Kumari and Sharma (2017) report that R&D has a statistically insignificant, negative coefficient when investigating determinants of FDI. However, R&D is found elsewhere to be positively associated with FDI (Singhania and Gupta, 2011). This contrasting finding is despite the same variable being used as a proxy for R&D and therefore is likely due to the regions analysed. Singhania and Gupta (2011) focus solely on FDI determinants for India whereas Kumari and Sharma (2017) investigate the determinants for a range of developing countries. This conveys the lack of clarity in the existing literature over the role R&D plays in determining FDI. Research from Park, Lee and Lee (2022) highlights this complexity, with varying conclusions based on whether private or public R&D spending in the host country is considered. Public R&D is found to induce inward R&D FDI for developing countries but not for developed countries. However, this conclusion is specific to R&D FDI so the same results may not be significant when looking at the effect of public R&D on total FDI. The impact of economic variables, such as R&D, on FDI is often ambiguous as is the extent to which political variables have an effect.

Host countries' risk, a more political variable, is found to not be a significant determinant by Bevan and Estrin (2004) compared to proximity and market size. This study uses bilateral flows of FDI but is limited in its relevance as it focusses mainly on FDI from Western countries to Central and Eastern Europe. Therefore, it may not be applicable to determinants of FDI for all countries. Blonigen and Piger (2014) also do not find robust evidence that host-country institutions encourage FDI into a country in their study. They use Bayesian statistical techniques to find the variables most likely to affect FDI activity, which allows comparisons to be made between a larger set of potential determinants than is often seen in the literature. The authors conclude that political institutions are not particularly important as a driver of FDI. However, contrasting findings for the importance of institutions are seen in literature that focusses specifically on Chinese investment (Buckley et al., 2007; Kolstad and Wiig, 2012). Later in this section, this is discussed further.

As previously mentioned, findings of important determinants in general FDI literature

may not be applicable to the determinants of Chinese foreign investment. Mumtaz and Smith (2018) find regional differences in the determinants of FDI investment from China and Zhang, X. and Daly (2011) find significant differences between China's and developed economies' OFDI. This demonstrates that conclusions from the extensive literature on FDI determinants across the globe should not automatically be applied to the topic of this dissertation. Although the studies discussed are noteworthy, the extensive literature focussed specifically on determinants of Chinese FDI is more relevant.

3.2 Findings on key determinants of Chinese FDI in existing literature

The rise in FDI coming from China has encouraged a range of studies investigating the possible causes and consequences. Academic literature has explored the determinants of Chinese FDI across the world as well as in specific regions, such as Europe.

Abu Dayeh and Janičo (2021) focus on Chinese investment in the Central and Eastern Europe region estimating a FE model with macroeconomic and institutional variables that they split into resource-, efficiency-, and market-seeking motivations following Dunning and Narula (2003). They conclude that access to the EU market is a key determinant in this region. This is unsurprising when considering how important market-seeking incentives, often represented by market size, are found to be across the literature. Their research also provides other interesting and less widespread findings.

The authors find that R&D spending is one of the most important drivers of Chinese investment. Gammeltoft and Fasshauer (2017) add more nuance to this conclusion as they find a positive relationship between R&D expenditures and Chinese FDI in Eastern Europe but not for Western Europe. This difference is likely down to regional differences but could also be driven by the level of detail in the analysis. Gammeltoft and Fasshauer (2017) perform a company-level analysis, estimating regressions for different clusters of Chinese companies to reach their conclusions whereas Abu Dayeh and Janičo (2021) use aggregate dependent and explanatory variables in their regressions. Nevertheless, these results demonstrate the sensitivity of conclusions in the current literature to the region focussed on and the uncertainty of R&D as a key determinant. However, other variables are found to consistently be important determinants of Chinese FDI.

In both studies mentioned above, GDP is found to be a significant factor with a positive impact on FDI, reinforcing the importance of market-seeking behaviour as a determinant. Shuyan and Fabuš (2019) also find GDP, representing market size, to be the most important factor influencing Chinese investment into Europe. The regularity of this finding amongst a wide range of studies, including those similar to this research project, is clear. The impact of GDP is well established but is not the only factor that is found to have a positive effect on Chinese FDI.

Zhang, X. and Daly (2011) present the result that high volumes of exports to China attract Chinese FDI. The authors conclude that a strong trade relationship encourages FDI, but the trade variables used are measured as aggregate values. Consequently, they could be representing the total volume of trade more than the strength of the trade relationship specifically with China. Therefore, the association found could be attributed to market-seeking behaviour, with Chinese companies investing in countries that have high volumes of global exports ensuring greater access to markets. This is a finding replicated by Abu Dayeh and Janičo (2021) measuring trade as the ratio of the sum of exports and imports to host country GDP which again represents overall trade openness rather than a trade relationship with China. While trade openness is widely found to be a determinant of Chinese FDI, variables chosen in the existing literature are limited in providing insights to the benefits of a strong trade relationship with China. Using a different variable could be more reliable in indicating the importance of a close trade relationship with China as a determinant of Chinese FDI.

Institutions, a more political variable, are also often cited as a potential determinant of FDI. Buckley et al. (2007) find that both economic and political aggregate variables are associated with Chinese OFDI. The authors claim that high political risk in a host country encourages Chinese investment. The goal of the paper is to provide research for understanding the OFDI strategies of emerging markets. However, one could argue that China should no longer be seen as an emerging market. Therefore, factors driving their outward investment may have changed implying this study is outdated. The study only looks at data from 1984 to 2001 and since this period, the volume and importance of Chinese FDI has transformed. Kolstad and Wiig (2012) also find that Chinese FDI is attracted to countries with poor institutions. Again, the relevance of their findings today may be limited as they study the period between 2003 and 2006. Zhang, Y., Li and Zhang

(2024) investigate the impact of institutional quality in the host country on China's FDI using more recent data and find a nuanced result. They conclude higher institutional quality positively affects investment if there is a market-seeking motive but negatively affects investment if the motive is natural resource-seeking. This is an insightful result, but the authors only focus on institutions and make no attempt to find the relative importance of institutions compared to other determinants. Therefore, the extent to which investment decisions are driven by this variable, potentially implying political motivations is not made clearer.

Non-economic motivations for investment from China have also been explored with respect to the BRI, since it was introduced in 2013. Du and Zhang (2018) evidence that Chinese FDI, particularly M&A, rose significantly following the announcement. However, Kang et al. (2018) find that once heterogeneity amongst BRI and non-BRI countries is controlled for, the difference in the amount of FDI received from China disappears. The authors argue that the initiative is the continuation of institutional cooperation rather than a policy shock that has altered the direction of Chinese FDI. However, the time period analysed is only from 2010 to 2015 and the BRI's impact on Chinese FDI may need longer than two years to be seen. Furthermore, neither of these studies attempt to examine the relative importance of being part of the BRI. There is little existing literature which seeks to explore the importance of political variables in comparison to economic variables as they are often researched separately.

Although, the relative importance of political and economic variables may not be mentioned, academic papers exploring the key determinants of Chinese investment sometimes provide conclusions on the overall motivations behind Chinese FDI. In studies specific to investigating the determinants of investment in Europe, Gammeltoft and Fasshauer (2017) find market-seeking motivations drive investment by Chinese companies but Abu Dayeh and Janíčo (2021) propose that these motivations in the Central and Eastern Europe region are not entirely confirmed. Cheung and Qian (2009) examine drivers of Chinese FDI globally and conclude that resource-seeking as well as market-seeking motives are behind Chinese investment. These conclusions often refer to the resource-seeking, efficiency-seeking or market-seeking motivations outlined by Dunning and Lundan (2008). The current literature does not extend this to whether the key determinants imply economic or political motivations.

3.3 This study's contribution to existing literature

The changing volumes and importance of Chinese FDI into Europe and beyond result in the need for consistent attention to the possibility of changing motivations and drivers of investment. This study not only contributes to the literature with up-to-date research on the determinants, but also with its use of a dataset built from deal-level verification, provided by Fathom Consulting (2024). The importance of using unbiased Chinese OFDI data is often disregarded in existing literature (Sutherland and Anderson, 2015) and the choice of dataset ensures the results found in this study are reliable. This will help provide a clearer picture of what determines Chinese FDI into the EU.

In addition, previous studies, mentioned throughout this section, have often only focussed on determinants of total FDI. Alon, Elia and Li (2020) identify that the use of greenfield investments is frequently missing from analysis in existing literature. Due to the detail of the dataset used, this dissertation can provide more detailed insights than the current literature. Dividing total Chinese FDI into the EU into greenfield and M&A deals allows for further conclusions on how determinants may differ for these types of investment.

This research also contributes to the existing literature by providing insights into the relative importance of the determinants. Economic variables alone may not be able to explain how Chinese FDI is distributed as geopolitical objectives are also found to be a factor affecting where Chinese companies invest (Dos Santos and Milan, 2014). This study investigates the relative importance of key economic as well as political variables, discussed in previous literature, in encouraging FDI from China into the EU. From the results, comparisons can be made using a more reliable dataset and longer time frame than previous research with implications of whether economic or political motivations are more significant for Chinese investment in the EU.

4. Data

This dissertation uses a panel of 28 EU members covering the time period from 2005 to 2023, collated using multiple different sources. The FDI data is sourced from Fathom's China Capital Flows Tracker (Fathom Consulting, 2024) which improves upon data used in previous literature due to its meticulous detail. It is constructed using deal-level data, in a bottom-up deal-by-deal approach to provide the best measure possible of China's

OFDI. The value and number of deals are provided for total FDI, greenfield and M&A investment, which are the dependent variables in this analysis. Greenfield investment is defined as the creation of a new subsidiary and the related facilities as well as the expansion of existing production or operational facilities (Fathom Consulting, 2024). M&A deals are defined as a merger or acquisition of at least 10% of the equity or assets of an existing company (Fathom Consulting, 2024). This dataset guides the data selection, with the time period studied selected because the dataset begins in 2005 and ends in 2023. The dataset also provides annual data for each country and therefore the frequency of the data collected for explanatory variables is annual.

The explanatory variables chosen are those that are often identified as key determinants of FDI in the existing literature, discussed in section 3. Relevant studies identifying these determinants as important are displayed in Table 3. Furthermore, the determinants chosen could be seen to represent economic and political motivations, potentially allowing the relative significance of these motivations to be explored. The expected relationship between Chinese FDI and each variable is also presented in the table and is predicted due to the results in the relevant literature for that variable. A range of different sources are used for the explanatory variables which are also included in Table 3 along with a description of each variable. The sources are chosen to provide broad coverage and sensible interpretations of what could drive Chinese FDI into the EU.

Table 3 - Summary of the explanatory variables

Variable	Expected Sign	Relevant literature	Description	Source
GDP	+	(Shuyan and Fabuš, 2019) (Abu Dayeh and Janičo, 2021)	Gross Domestic Product. That is, the sum of gross value added by all resident producers in the economy in current U.S. dollars.	World Bank (2024a)
Trade	+	(Zhang, X. and Daly, 2011) (Abu Dayeh and Janičo, 2021)	The sum of exports and imports to and from China as a per cent of exports and imports to and from the world.	International Monetary Fund (2024)
BRI	+	(Du and Zhang, 2018)	A dummy variable of whether a country had signed a memorandum of understanding joining the BRI at that point in time. 1 if yes, 0 if no.	Nedopil (2025)
R&D	+	(Abu Dayeh and Janičo, 2021) (Gammeltoft and Fasshauer, 2017)	Government budget allocations for R&D (GBARD) as a per cent of total government expenditure.	Eurostat (2024)
Institutions	-	(Buckley et al., 2007) (Kolstad and Wiig, 2012)	An index formed from an average of six dimensions of governance for each year and country. The dimensions are Voice and Accountability, Political Stability and Absence of Violence/Terrorism, Government Effectiveness, Regulatory Quality, Rule of Law, and Control of Corruption.	World Bank (2024b)

The panel data used in this analysis is slightly unbalanced due to missing observations for the R&D variable for Croatia and the UK in the years when they were not EU members. For all other variables, the dataset has full coverage. The dataset is a short panel, with a larger number of countries than time periods, that is 28 EU countries with 19 years included.

Natural logarithms are taken of the three dependent variables as well as the GDP and institutions variables. This both controls for extreme values and allows for results of the regressions to be interpreted as elasticities (Wooldridge, 2018). All other variables are either already in percentage form or are dummy variables so natural logarithms are not taken.

Prior to performing any regressions, a correlation matrix is made of the control and explanatory variables to check for any multicollinearity, displayed in Table 9 in the Appendix. No significant multicollinearity is present for the explanatory variables which allows for improved estimations (Wooldridge, 2018).

5. Econometric approach

The same econometric approach is repeated with total FDI, greenfield and M&A investment as the dependent variables allowing for comparisons to be drawn between them. Furthermore, the same approach is repeated using the value and number of deals as a measurement for these dependent variables. All regressions conform to the following models:

$$\ln FDI_{it} = EU_{it} + \ln GDP_{it} + Trade_{it} + R\&D_{it} + BRI_{it} + \ln Institutions_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

$$\ln GF_{it} = EU_{it} + \ln GDP_{it} + Trade_{it} + R\&D_{it} + BRI_{it} + \ln Institutions_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

$$\ln MA_{it} = EU_{it} + \ln GDP_{it} + Trade_{it} + R\&D_{it} + BRI_{it} + \ln Institutions_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Where

$\ln FDI_{it}$, $\ln GF_{it}$, $\ln MA_{it}$ are the natural logarithms of total, greenfield and M&A FDI from China respectively and are the dependent variables in the models. EU_{it} is a dummy variable of whether the country is a member of the EU in each given year, acting as a control variable. $\ln GDP_{it}$ and $\ln Institutions_{it}$ represent the natural logarithms of the GDP and institutions variables, described in Table 3, respectively. $Trade_{it}$, $R\&D_{it}$, BRI_{it} represent the trade, R&D and BRI variables respectively which are also described in Table 3 and ε_{it} is an error term with the subscripts i and t representing the country and year respectively.

Regression analysis is used as it is identified in previous literature as the best empirical method to determine which host country factors attract Chinese FDI (Gammeltoft and

Fasshauer, 2017). Multiple regressions are estimated to investigate the drivers behind China’s FDI in the EU. Initially, a pooled OLS regression is estimated to establish a baseline. A time-FE model is estimated since Chinese OFDI varies from year-to-year and these variations are not necessarily driven by changing economic or political factors across the EU but global factors or domestic factors in China (Cheung and Qian, 2009).

A RE model with a time component is also estimated for each dependent variable. Table 4 displays the results of the Hausman test for the time FE and RE models using both the value of and number of deals measurements for the dependent variables. When the Hausman test returns a p-value below 0.05, there is evidence to reject the RE model and the FE model should be used, whereas a failure to reject the RE assumptions implies the two models are sufficiently close and either can be used (Wooldridge, 2018). Table 4 illustrates that the FE model should be used for all dependent variables when they are measured in the value of deals and when M&A is the dependent variable measured in the number of deals. However, with total FDI and greenfield FDI as dependent variables measured in the number of deals, either model can be used. For consistency, the estimates of the FE model are most closely considered in this paper’s analysis.

Table 4 - Hausman test results for the time-FE vs RE models

Dependent variable	p-value	Meaning
Value of deals		
Total FDI	0.00 < 0.05	Use FE model
Greenfield	0.03 < 0.05	Use FE model
M&A	0.00 < 0.05	Use FE model
Number of deals		
Total FDI	0.27 > 0.05	Use RE or FE model
Greenfield	0.60 > 0.05	Use RE or FE model
M&A	0.00 < 0.05	Use FE model

Heteroskedasticity is tested for with a Breusch-Pagan test and autocorrelation is tested for with a Woolridge test. Both these tests are suggested by Wooldridge (2018). Evidence of both heteroskedasticity and autocorrelation is identified in the FE models across all dependent variables using both measurements except where the value of M&A deals is the dependent variable. The results are presented in Tables 10 and 11 in the Appendix.

Consequently, estimates using panel-corrected standard errors (SE) are produced to improve the reliability (Beck and Katz, 1995).

Furthermore, a time FE model with explanatory variables lagged by a year is also estimated to mitigate the threat of reverse causality (Bellemare, Masaki and Pepinsky, 2017). Reverse causality is a concern for this model, especially for GDP as substantial inward FDI is likely to improve a country's output (Batten and Vo, 2009) causing potential issues of endogeneity. Furthermore, investment decisions are rarely made and announced within a year. Economic variables from the year before may then be a better representation of the drivers behind Chinese FDI into the EU. However, as is displayed in the following section, the results for all models estimated are similar.

6. Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of the regression analysis undertaken for the three dependent variables: FDI, greenfield and M&A deals. The results of multiple regression models are presented for both the value and count of Chinese FDI deals into the EU. Tables 5, 6 and 7 present these results for the value of total FDI, greenfield and M&A deals respectively. Table 8 presents a summary of the results using the number of deals to measure the dependent variables. Following this, the potential implications about the motivations behind Chinese FDI in the EU are discussed.

Tables 5, 6 and 7 report the results of the Pooled OLS regression in column 1, time-FE model (with and without panel-corrected SE) in 2 and 4 respectively, RE model with time-varying components in 3 and lagged time-FE model in column 5.

6.1 Value of Chinese FDI deals measurement

We first look at the results measuring the dependent variables using the value of deals. As discussed in the previous section, the Hausman test confirmed that the time-FE model is appropriate and preferred to the RE model. Estimates from the time FE regression with panel-corrected SE are referred to in this section as they make the most intuitive sense while providing robustness, as explained in section 5. However, as previously stated, the results are largely consistent regardless of the model used.

Table 5 - Impact of Economic and Political Factors on Chinese total FDI in the EU

	1	2	3	4	5
GDP	1.272*** (0.062)	1.229*** (0.058)	1.247*** (0.058)	1.223*** (0.081)	1.220*** (0.060)
Trade	0.173*** (0.045)	0.046 (0.046)	0.093** (0.045)	0.046 (0.062)	0.056 (0.048)
R&D	-0.621** (0.260)	-0.699*** (0.240)	-0.667** (0.243)	-0.699** (0.350)	-0.700*** (0.249)
BRI	0.119 (0.213)	-0.72*** (0.273)	-0.365 (0.248)	-0.721** (0.286)	-1.128*** (0.289)
Institutions	0.235 (0.158)	0.302** (0.147)	0.285* (0.148)	0.302 (0.193)	0.206 (0.150)
R ²	0.51	0.55	0.53		0.55
Observations	525	525	525	525	498
Time-Fixed effects	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes

Standard errors are reported in parenthesis.

*(***), (**) and (*) refer to the 1%, 5% and 10% significance levels respectively.*

1: Pooled regression 2: Time FE regression 3: RE regression 4: Time FE regression with panel-corrected SE 5: Time FE regression with one-year lag.

It is GDP that stands out as the most important variable in determining Chinese FDI across the EU. The coefficients are statistically significant at the 1% level for all estimates and for all dependent variables. Looking at total FDI in Table 5, on average, a 1% increase in a country's GDP leads to a 1.22% increase in the value of deals in a given year.

The magnitude of the GDP coefficients in comparison to other variables demonstrates the importance of market size in attracting Chinese investment compared to other factors. The positive impact of GDP is expected and could represent market-seeking incentives, where FDI is driven by a desire to gain access to large and developed markets. This finding is commonly seen in the existing literature (Gammeltoft and Fasshauer, 2017; Shuyan and Fabuš, 2019; Abu Dayeh and Janičo, 2021). High economic output and activity will provide plenty of opportunities for investment which Chinese companies evidently seek to exploit. Investing in high GDP countries also gives Chinese companies access to more qualified human capital, higher productivity and a wealthier domestic

market (Ghazalian, 2024). In addition, a more developed market is also associated with lower levels of risk further encouraging investment (Vijayakumar, Rasheed and Tondkar, 2009). The benefits that come with investing in a strong economy are seemingly what dominates investment decision making for Chinese companies in the EU.

R&D investment by a country's government is found to have a statistically significant negative effect on receiving Chinese FDI, seen in Table 5. This contrasts with the findings of Abu Dayeh and Janičo (2021) who find that R&D expenditures are a key driver of Chinese FDI in Central and Eastern Europe. The opposing findings could be driven by the countries analysed as this dissertation also includes Western European members of the EU. Gammeltoft and Fasshauer (2017) find a positive relationship between R&D spending and Chinese FDI in Eastern Europe but not for Western Europe suggesting that it is the countries included that causes the differing results.

The BRI represents a possible political determinant of Chinese investment across the EU (Kang et al., 2018). However, there is a statistically significant negative coefficient found for all dependent variables, contradicting the expected impact of the BRI as it aims to promote investment and development (Tritto and Camba, 2023). This could be capturing other characteristics of non-BRI countries, potentially related to being the most developed countries in the EU, that drive Chinese FDI. For example, highly developed countries such as France, Germany and the UK, are not part of the BRI (Nedopil, 2025) and receive large volumes of Chinese investment flows, as seen in Table 1. Factors that contribute to their development, thus making it less likely they are part of the BRI but are not captured in the GDP variable, may be causing the negative relationship found. It should also be considered that this is a study on determinants of Chinese FDI into the EU. Therefore, this finding does not imply that the BRI has no effect on Chinese FDI but that its effect is at best negligible for investment in the EU.

Table 6 - Impact of Economic and Political Factors on Chinese Greenfield FDI in the EU

	1	2	3	4	5
GDP	1.079*** (0.057)	1.031*** (0.055)	1.054*** (0.055)	1.031*** (0.079)	1.036*** (0.056)
Trade	0.114*** (0.041)	0.026 (0.044)	0.070* (0.042)	0.026 (0.068)	0.05 (0.045)
R&D	-0.538** (0.238)	-0.582** (0.226)	-0.554** (0.228)	-0.582* (0.349)	-0.555** (0.235)
BRI	0.182 (0.195)	-0.753*** (0.257)	-0.288 (0.227)	-0.753* (0.447)	-0.846*** (0.273)
Institutions	-0.229 (0.145)	-0.233* (0.138)	-0.232* (0.139)	-0.233 (0.207)	-0.292** (0.141)
R ²	0.45	0.48	0.46		0.48
Observations	525	525	525	525	498
Time-Fixed effects	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes

Standard errors are reported in parenthesis.

*(***), (**) and (*) refer to the 1%, 5% and 10% significance levels respectively.*

1: Pooled regression 2: Time FE regression 3: RE regression 4: Time FE regression with panel-corrected SE 5: Time FE regression with one-year lag.

The positive effect of GDP on FDI reduces slightly when looking solely at greenfield investment. Table 6 shows that a 1% increase in GDP leads to a 1.03% increase in the value of greenfield FDI received from Chinese companies, on average. The estimate is smaller than the 1.22% increase reported as the impact of GDP on total FDI in Table 5. An explanation could be that resource-seeking incentives dominate market-seeking incentives for greenfield FDI investment (Marinescu, 2016), so GDP is slightly less important in this context.

A negative effect of high R&D spending is seen on greenfield investment as well as on total FDI investment. Table 6 suggests that a 1% increase in a government's share of expenditure on R&D, on average, leads to a 0.58% fall in greenfield FDI, which is a statistically significant result at the 5% level. As previously mentioned, this is an unexpected but not exceptional result. These findings could imply that a government

investing in R&D may crowd out Chinese FDI. Park, Lee and Lee (2022) find that public R&D can have a crowding-out effect on private R&D for developed countries. This may be true for foreign R&D investment too. Therefore, the negative coefficient may be due to the EU's composition of mainly developed countries which results in public R&D having a crowding-out effect.

Table 7 - Impact of Economic and Political Factors on Chinese M&A FDI in the EU

	1	2	3	4	5
GDP	1.236*** (0.071)	1.208*** (0.067)	1.224*** (0.067)	1.208*** (0.122)	1.209*** (0.068)
Trade	0.271*** (0.051)	0.135** (0.03)	0.195*** (0.051)	0.135** (0.061)	0.135** (0.054)
R&D	-0.366 (0.298)	-0.453 (0.276)	-0.411 (0.281)	-0.453 (0.484)	-0.519* (0.283)
BRI	-0.057 (0.244)	-0.675** (0.314)	-0.327 (0.278)	-0.675* (0.346)	-0.827** (0.328)
Institutions	0.574*** (0.181)	0.686*** (0.169)	0.647*** (0.171)	0.686*** (0.188)	0.709*** (0.170)
R ²	0.47	0.51	0.49		0.52
Observations	525	525	525	525	498
Time-Fixed effects	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes

Standard errors are reported in parenthesis.

*(***), (**) and (*) refer to the 1%, 5% and 10% significance levels respectively.*

1: Pooled regression 2: Time FE regression 3: RE regression 4: Time FE regression with panel-corrected SE 5: Time FE regression with one-year lag.

GDP also has a strong impact on Chinese FDI when looking solely at M&A deals. Table 7 presents the finding that a 1% increase in a country's GDP leads to a 1.21% increase in the value of M&A deals, on average, in a given year. This further conveys the importance of market size in determining Chinese FDI across the EU.

Trade is not found to be an important determinant for the value of Chinese FDI deals in the EU as its estimates lack magnitude and statistical significance. However, with M&A investment as the dependent variable, a positive effect is seen when a higher share of a

country's trade is with China. A closer trade relationship could be attractive for Chinese investors, who may see opportunities to apply their knowledge and build on established networks with China. The apparent weakness of trade as a determinant of total FDI in this study contrasts with the stronger findings of Zhang, X. and Daly (2011). The authors find that a close trade relationship with China encourages FDI but this difference in conclusion may be down to the variables used. Their trade variable is measured by aggregate exports to China which may represent overall trade openness. Contrastingly, the variable used in this dissertation is measured by the share of a country's total trade that is with China, representing the strength of their trade ties with China. Zhang, X. and Daly (2011) do not find imports to be statistically significant indicating that the results in this dissertation are weaker due to the variable used which incorporates total trade rather than only exports.

Institutions are found to have a positive effect on Chinese M&A investment. Table 7 shows that a 1% increase in the institutions index, on average, leads to a 0.69% increase in the value of M&A deals from China. This result is statistically significant at the 1% level and holds across multiple regression models. Contrastingly, there is no such finding for greenfield investment in Table 6. This suggests Chinese enterprises pay more attention to the institutions where companies they are merging with or acquiring are based, compared to the institutions where they are building capital. When looking at a company to acquire or merge with, the country's institutions may provide confidence for investment but are not as relevant for building capital i.e., greenfield investment. This paper's finding that institutional factors influence Chinese M&A investment in the EU, but not greenfield FDI, aligns with the conclusions of Zhang, Y., Li and Zhang (2024). The authors find that higher institutional quality positively affects investment if there is a market-seeking motive but has a negative effect if the motive is natural resource-seeking. Considering M&A FDI is found to be driven more by market-seeking incentives (Marinescu, 2016), our findings are consistent with those of Zhang, Y., Li and Zhang (2024).

This is an unexpected finding and contrasts with research by Buckley et al. (2007) and Kolstad and Wiig (2012) who find that poor institutions attract Chinese investment but these studies focus on Chinese OFDI globally. Therefore, the difference in conclusion could be due to this dissertation focussing on determinants in the EU, where poor

institutions may no longer be an important determinant of investment. In addition, it could also be as a result of this paper breaking down FDI into M&A and greenfield investment. This allows more precise relationships, such as that between Chinese M&A FDI and institutions in the EU, to be identified.

6.2 Number of Chinese FDI deals measurement

The previous results use the value of deals as the dependent variable, but it is worthwhile to also look at the number of deals to investigate the importance of economic determinants for Chinese FDI. Overall market activity may be seen more by the number of deals as a small number of large investments could skew the analysis of what drives Chinese investment if looking solely at the value of deals. However, there is no consensus best way to measure FDI (Wacker, 2013), so considering both the number of and value of deals measurements provides robustness to this dissertation's results and builds a more complete analysis. Table 8 summarises the results for each of the dependent variables from the time FE regression model with panel-corrected SE using the number of deals as the measurement.

Table 8 - Results of the time-FE regression using number of deals measurement

	Total FDI	Greenfield	M&A
GDP	0.648*** (0.053)	0.527*** (0.062)	0.454*** (0.065)
Trade	0.101*** (0.382)	0.103** (0.045)	0.109*** (0.031)
R&D	-0.132 (0.196)	-0.029 (0.236)	-0.034 (0.211)
BRI	-0.407*** (0.136)	-0.382** (0.188)	-0.322** (0.147)
Institutions	0.073 (0.126)	-0.013 (0.135)	-0.084 (0.110)

Standard errors are reported in parenthesis.

*(***), (**) and (*) refer to the 1%, 5% and 10% significance levels respectively.*

Model estimated with panel-corrected SE.

Results share some similarities with the findings when measuring the dependent variables with the value of deals. Crucially, GDP is the largest significant factor again, although

the magnitude decreases. Table 8 shows that a 1% increase in GDP, on average, leads to a 0.65% increase in the number of deals. This is smaller than the increase in the value of total FDI deals that is found in Table 5. The pattern of a smaller but still positive coefficient for GDP remains with greenfield and M&A investment as the dependent variables. The smaller coefficient could be a result of high value deals being concentrated in higher GDP countries. For example, in the China Capital Flows dataset used, eight out of the ten highest value investments into the EU were into Germany or the UK (Fathom Consulting, 2024). Regardless of magnitude, the positive statistically significant coefficient further suggests market-seeking behaviour from Chinese companies when investing in the EU.

When looking in terms of the number of deals, a statistically significant relationship between all dependent variables and trade is now seen. The significance persists in different types of models, but its smaller magnitude suggests trade relationships are not as crucial as GDP in determining Chinese FDI in the EU. Nevertheless, these results now align more closely with the previously discussed work of Zhang, X. and Daly (2011).

Again, being part of the BRI is seen to have a negative effect on a country's FDI received from China, but the effect is smaller in magnitude. This is statistically significant at the 5% level for all dependent variables where, on average, being part of the BRI is associated with approximately a 0.41% fall in the number of total FDI deals, shown in Table 8.

Results using the number of deals measurement contrast to those measuring FDI by the value of deals for institutions. The variable is not a statistically significant determinant for the number of M&A deals as it was for the value of deals. This could indicate that institutions are a more important determinant for larger value investments.

These results confirm the findings, from the analysis using the value of deals, that economic variables are the key determinants of Chinese FDI into the EU. The significance of GDP as a determinant is crucial and outweighs all other variables. Although political variables such as institutions are found to have an effect, the estimated impacts are not as strong and broad as for GDP or trade and a negative effect of being part of the BRI is also seen. The conclusions of the key determinants being economic variables could imply that political motivations are outweighed by economic motivations when it comes to foreign investment decisions from Chinese companies.

6.3 Implications for the motivations behind Chinese FDI

It is indicated that Chinese companies mostly exhibit market-seeking behaviour when investing in the EU. Although this is found by other studies, they have also provided evidence of strategic asset- or natural resource-seeking behaviour (Kolstad and Wiig, 2012; Blomkvist and Rian, 2016). This dissertation’s findings do not disregard the possibilities of this but rather suggest that economic motivations appear more apparent than political motivations from the key determinants found.

Economic motivations may seem to be more common for Chinese investments in aggregate, but there could still be political and strategic investments in the EU. Figure 4 displays the strong correlation in 2023 between Chinese investment and GDP, as is expected from this paper’s findings. However, market-seeking motivations may not always explain investments, as seen in the case of Hungary. Hungary is an outlier to this correlation which may imply that the investments here are driven by strategic rather than economic motivations. For example, Völgyi and Lukács (2021) find that Chinese investments in Hungary have been positively influenced by political meetings and strategic cooperation agreements.

Figure 4 - Chinese total FDI across the EU and GDP, 2023

Source: Fathom Consulting (2024) / World Bank (2024a)

Therefore, while the results in this paper imply that political determinants have a limited effect on aggregate Chinese investment in the EU, concerns over Chinese OFDI should not be forgotten. Instead, focus should be more specific to investments in countries where there may not be market-seeking motivations or focussed on investments in key sectors.

7. Conclusion

This dissertation has examined the importance of key economic and political determinants for Chinese FDI into the EU. By leveraging data from Fathom Consulting's (2024) China Capital Flows Tracker, the study distinguishes between total, greenfield, and M&A investment flows for more nuanced results too. Time-FE regression models are employed with the results suggesting that economic determinants are the primary drivers of Chinese FDI in the EU.

The strength of the relationship found for GDP and total, greenfield and M&A FDI strongly suggests that market-seeking behaviour has a key influence on the investments of Chinese enterprises. Trade with China is also found to have a positive effect on the number of FDI deals for all dependent variables, indicating that more trade with China may stimulate market activity from Chinese companies. The role of political determinants is more limited. For example, institutions are only found to be a key driver for M&A FDI and may be determining investment as a signal of stability rather than implying strategic motivations. A notable and unexpected finding is that being part of the BRI is associated with fewer FDI deals, possibly due to the most developed EU countries not being part of the BRI. This further reinforces the importance of economic over political determinants. R&D government expenditure has a negative effect on the value of greenfield FDI deals which is also an unexpected finding. The complexity of some results suggest that economic variables are not unequivocally more important than political variables in encouraging Chinese investment across the EU. Nonetheless, this study concludes that economic determinants remain the most significant influences on Chinese FDI in the EU.

EU policymakers' concerns over increasing Chinese OFDI may be alleviated slightly by the findings that economic determinants are the key drivers of Chinese FDI for this region. This investigation provides no evidence of Chinese investment being politically driven or strategic at the aggregate level. Consequently, the findings of this paper do not support any policies that would 'de-risk' by putting restrictions on all FDI received from China, for example.

Political variables are found to play more of a role in determining M&A FDI in this study but not in a sense that implies strategic motivations. A positive relationship between institutions and M&A investment in the EU is found, contradicting the hypothesis that

China strategically invests in countries with poor institutions as is suggested in the existing literature (Buckley et al., 2007; Kolstad and Wiig, 2012). Therefore, this paper's findings do not provide any reason for concern over EU members receiving FDI from China.

However, there could still be some investments from Chinese MNCs in the EU which grant China geopolitical influence. Policies to mitigate the threat of Chinese companies having geopolitical influence should be specific to sectors that the EU is looking to protect or at a deal-level where the intentions are questionable. These policies can be assisted by the encouragement of more studies similar to that of Otero-Iglesias and Weissenegger (2020), who investigate which transactions by Chinese enterprises in the EU justify apprehension. Concerns over strategic investments should also be directed where large volumes of investment are not determined by the key economic variables found in this study. The example of Hungary being an outlier in terms of the relationship between inward FDI flows from China and its market size is presented in section 6.3. This could be one example where EU policymakers should be wary of political motivations, but further investigation is necessary before any action.

One limitation for this dissertation is the small number of explanatory variables used in the model. This results in low multicollinearity and simple interpretability but does reduce the explanatory power of the model, with the R-squared values around 50%. There could be omitted variables that are determinants of FDI so future research may wish to include additional variables for a wider scope. Variables that represent natural resource endowments could be included to allow for a conclusion on whether Chinese investment is natural resource-seeking as well as market-seeking in the EU, as is found by Kolstad and Wiig (2012) for Chinese OFDI globally.

Furthermore, whether these variables are economic or political determinants is not always clear. For example, trade with China is viewed as an economic determinant in this study but could stem from political decisions such as trade liberalising measures. Therefore, this paper should be viewed as identifying key determinants which imply economic motivations rather than identifying economic motivations. In addition, the measurements of these explanatory variables could be questioned. One measurement is used for each variable and although they are chosen to provide the best coverage and intuitive sense, additional robustness could be evidenced by repeating the analysis with different

measurements used in other studies.

Furthermore, although this paper provides more detail on the varying determinants for different forms of Chinese FDI, this could be taken further. Future research could provide additional insights by investigating how determinants vary across different sectors. Fathom Consulting's (2024) deal-level China Capital Flows dataset could be used to allow for research exploring whether investments in strategic sectors, such as Energy, are driven by market-seeking behaviour or if political determinants are more important here.

Another possibility to extend the findings of this research could be creating a more dynamic model. Future research could group years to identify if key determinants have changed over time, possibly becoming more political in recent years. However, this would reduce the statistical power of the model because the number of observations i.e., the sample size would be reduced (Wooldridge, 2018). These extensions would allow for more refined findings to build on this paper's conclusions that, in aggregate, economic determinants exert the greatest influence on Chinese FDI into the EU.

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Appendix

Table 9 - Correlation matrix of control and explanatory variables

	EU	GDP	Trade	R&D	BRI	Institutions
EU	1	0.116	-0.011	0.002	0.075	0.303
GDP	0.116	1	0.044	0.442	-0.173	0.224
Trade	-0.011	0.044	1	0.090	-0.022	0.121
R&D	0.002	0.442	0.090	1	-0.173	0.526
BRI	0.075	-0.173	-0.022	-0.173	1	-0.239
Institutions	0.303	0.224	0.121	0.526	-0.239	1

Table 10 – Breusch-Pagan test results for heteroskedasticity

Dependent variable	p-value	Evidence of heteroskedasticity?
Value of deals		
Total FDI	0.01 < 0.05	Yes
Greenfield	0.00 < 0.05	Yes
M&A	0.25 > 0.05	No
Number of deals		
Total FDI	0.00 < 0.05	Yes
Greenfield	0.00 < 0.05	Yes
M&A	0.00 < 0.05	Yes

Table 11 – Woolridge test results for autocorrelation

Dependent variable	p-value	Evidence of autocorrelation?
Value of deals		
Total FDI	0.00 < 0.05	Yes
Greenfield	0.00 < 0.05	Yes
M&A	0.00 < 0.05	Yes
Number of deals		
Total FDI	0.00 < 0.05	Yes
Greenfield	0.00 < 0.05	Yes
M&A	0.00 < 0.05	Yes